

Library Website Features as Indicators of Academic Excellence: A Study of Select Institutions of Eminence in India

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Abstract

This study evaluates the library websites of the Birla Institute of Technology and Science (Pilani, Rajasthan), Manipal Academy of Higher Education (Manipal, Karnataka), OP Jindal Global University (Sonapat, Haryana), and Shiv Nadar University (Greater Noida, NCR) using qualitative (11 checkpoints) and quantitative (170 checkpoints) methods. The qualitative analysis focused on 11 homepage features, capturing descriptive information. The quantitative analysis involved 170 dichotomous questions covering various aspects, including multimedia, general information, services, resources, library features, Web 2.0/Library 2.0 features, currency, accuracy, relevance, organizational structure, links, maintenance, user interface, search features, and feedback and support. A 5-point rating scale was used to assign numerical values to each feature, enabling their ranking based on the collected data.

This study highlights that library websites do not fully leverage Web 2.0 features. The overall scores for the library websites of BITSP, OPJGU, and SNUGN were 116 (68%), 125 (74%), and 131 (77%), respectively, placing them in the "Above Average" category (103–136 range).

Meanwhile, the MAHEM library website scored 78 (46%), categorizing it as "Average" (69–102 range). The study identified specific areas in these websites that need improvement to enhance user-friendliness and engagement. It can serve as a benchmark for assessing the development of other library websites and offers valuable insights into the characteristics of library websites in the context of ICT.

Keywords: Content, Websites, Evaluation, Library Webpages, BITSP, MAHEM, OPIGU, SNUGN, Institutions of Eminence in India.

1. Introduction

The advancement of information and communication technologies has empowered government organizations, businesses, educational institutions, and individuals to effectively share and present information using multimedia tools such as websites. Since websites are primarily visited for information retrieval, it is essential for them to offer content that is both valuable and useful to their visitors. The primary objective of a website is to provide relevant and meaningful information to all its stakeholders.

Indian educational institutions, particularly universities, utilize information and communication technology to achieve their goals by enhancing services, improving accessibility, and delivering content to stakeholders in electronic formats.

A library portal, website, or webpage typically serves as a centralized access point, integrating library catalogs, subscription databases, subject gateways, electronic journals, and other resources.

A website is a collection of interconnected web pages designed to convey a cohesive set of information. It can present content on its intended subject through text, graphics, audio, and sometimes videos.

Content and presentation are crucial in enhancing the usability of a library. A library website with rich and engaging content is more likely to attract and retain users.

Content analysis is a research method that involves observation and document review, providing an objective, systematic, and quantitative approach to describing the manifest content of communication.

2. Review of Literature

Evaluating websites is an essential skill in the era of digital and information literacy. The information provided on higher education institution websites is crucial for prospective students, research scholars, and aspiring faculty members. Most studies on institutional and university websites have predominantly concentrated on their information architecture. These websites are primarily designed to function as information hubs, catering especially to the needs of future students and scholars.

Rai, Singh & Lepcha (2023) examined “the content characteristics of the websites of the top five Indian Institutes of Technology (IIT) libraries, according to the NIRF ranking 2023. The study focuses primarily on the webpages of the selected IIT libraries, examining aspects such as webpage framework, style, layout, library services, and content. It explores how the IIT Library system employs rankings, services, print and electronic resources, and library technology solutions to support its users. The study indicates that IITs have satisfactory web-based tools and

services. Search and advanced search tools are implemented in almost all libraries, allowing users to browse available resources. Furthermore, every library website features hyperlinks to institutional repositories and open-access content. Based on the overall assessment, the IIT Delhi library website obtains the highest rating (77%), while the IIT Madras library website scores the lowest (60%) among the selected IIT libraries. The study suggests that these libraries should transition to the next level of high-tech services, such as dynamic websites, social media networks, and mobile applications, to meet the needs of young and emerging minds.”

Mehta, S. (2023) aimed to “evaluate the status of web-based library services at 14 IIMs located in different cities of India. The study adopted the evaluation method as a research methodology and designed a checklist that was categorized into twelve main themes: (i) multimedia features, (ii) general features, (iii) library service features, (iv) library resource features, (v) My Library and Training Programme Features, (vi) Web 2.0/Library 2.0, (vii) currency, accuracy, and relevance features, (viii) Organization and Structure, (ix) Links and Navigation, (x) Searching Features, (xi) Mobile Library Service Features, and (xii) User Interface/Support Features. The study mentioned that most library websites lie under the ‘average’ rank. In contrast, none of the libraries reaches the ‘excellent’ position, and a few library websites ought to fall under the ‘above average.’”

Gaurav et al. (2022) examined “the websites for the IIT library regarding content and design performance. For its distant readers who were looking for information, they recommended making the library websites' accessible features better.”

Rahman, A. and Batcha, M. S. (2020) conducted a “study on library websites of select colleges of Delhi University and found that the maximum number of college libraries have

mentioned information related to introduction 9(90 %), library staff 8(80 %), library hours 6(60 %) and membership 6(60 %) on their websites. However, the study also reported that none of the library websites/webpages have features of social networking tools, feedback, regular updates, and they also lack in providing question papers, news-clippings, user manuals, and single window searches. The study findings reveal that the Deshbandhu College library scored thirty eight (38) out of 43 which is the highest (ranked 1st) whereas Ramjas College scored only five (05) out of 43 and stood last. The study suggests, for carrying out such evaluative studies, which is the need of hour to enable the institutions to update their websites periodically and come up with flying colors on user's expectations.”

Bharati, S. K. and Madhusudhan, M.(2019) evaluated “the content of the Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU) and Banaras Hindu University (BHU) library websites using qualitative (11 checkpoints) and quantitative (170 checkpoints) evaluations. The qualitative parts covered 11 features which belong to the homepages of the websites, which helps as recording devices of the quantitative part of the checklists covered 170 dichotomous questions affiliated with different features, such as multimedia, general information, services, resources, library features, web2.0/library2.0 features, currency accuracy and relevance, organization and structure features, links and maintenance features, user-interface features, search features, and informative feedback and support features. A quantitative 5-points rating scales was used to provide a numerical rating for each feature and rank them on the basis of numerical facts. The study has shown that library websites are lagging behind to take full advantage of advance web2.0 features. Findings show that the JNU library website is scored 128 out of 170 (75.29%), which ranked above average, whereas BHU library website has ranked average by scoring 74 out of 170 (43.52%) features.”

Sahoo and Panda (2019) examined “the different types of library technology utilized by the IIT Bombay and IIT Delhi Library Systems. They discovered that IIT libraries use the most 4 recent technological advancements to provide their patrons with innovative library services.”

Sahoo (2019) used “common assessment standards to assess the web contents and browsing capabilities of the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) library portals. He discovered that none of the 18 IIT library websites met all the requirements established for the research, with 3 (16.7%) scoring only about 50 among the 100 checklist elements.”

Singh (2018) investigated “the usage of Web 2.0 tools in Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs) and Indian Institutes of Management (IIMs), including awareness of their existence and their prevalence. Additionally, it was shown that respondents were familiar with and used such programs in their academic and research projects.”

Devi, K. K. (2017) conducted “a research study on web content analysis of the Indian Institutes of Technologies (IITs) and National Institutes of Technology (NITs) libraries’ websites.”

Haridasan, S. and Uwesh, M. (2014) revealed “that most university library websites in India provide informative links to contacts, news, and events. Libraries should present different contact information (librarians, technical experts, circulation desks, digital services) on their websites. Some websites provide opportunities for user interaction in the form of feedback. Some library websites provide links to mission statements, locations, site maps, and library tours. A good number of the libraries provide the library hours, library rules and membership. These are useful features for quick page access. About 50 percent of the libraries provide some information about their history on their websites.”

Madhusudhan, M. and Ahmed. N. (2013) evaluated “multimedia features, content features, and user-interface features of IIMs library websites and used a qualitative and quantitative evaluation to cover four main criteria: technical description, multimedia features, library content features, and user-interface features. The study highlights how the features can open the door to librarians to explore the possibilities of communication, promotion, text responses, and catalogue access via mobile technology with the help of library websites”.

Pareek, S. and Gupta, D. K. (2013) conducted “a study on academic library websites in Rajasthan state and found that a small number of library websites can neither satisfy the efforts to bridge the digital divide nor represent a country with 170 million people.”

3. Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to analyze and compare the content features of the library websites of the following universities: Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani, Rajasthan (BITSP); Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka (MAHEM); OP Jindal Global University, Sonapat, Haryana (OPJGU); and Shiv Nadar University, Greater Noida, NCR (SNUGN).

The different content features of the above mentioned library websites;

- Identify the criteria for content analysis of Library websites under study;
- Evaluate the content features of library websites with the help of specially identified criteria for verification of validity, reliability, and usefulness;
- The different content features of the studied library websites were compared and ranked based on their features.

4. Scope of the Study

The Institutions of Eminence (IoE) in India libraries are taken for the study due to their importance as epitome of higher educational institutions comparable with same kind of institutions world wide. The Ministry of Education, Government of India has declared 12 public and private higher institutions as Institutions of Eminence (IoE) in India in the phased manner. This study includes only four private Institutions of Eminence in India as till date no study have been taken place for these institutions. (Table 1).

Table 1: List of Studied Institutions of Eminence in India

S.No.	Name of the Institution	Type	Year of establishment	Date of notification as IoE	website address/URL
1.	Birla Institute of Technology and Sciences, Pilani, Rajasthan	Private	1964	14.10.2020	www.bits-pilani.ac.in
2.	Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka	Private	1953	14.10.2020	www.manipal.edu
3.	OP Jindal Global University, Sonapat, Haryana	Private	2009	04.11.2020	www.jgu.edu.in
4.	Shiv Nadar University, Greater Noida,	Private	2011	03.08.2022	www.snu.edu.in

	NCR				
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5. Methodology

The criteria were established through a comprehensive review of the existing literature, encompassing studies conducted by Mehta (2023), Rahman and Batcha (2020), Bharati and Madhusudhan (2019), Devi and Verma (2018), Kaushik (2015), Madhusudhan and Ahmed (2013), and Madhusudhan (2012). These criteria have been significantly modified.

The assessment criteria in the study were categorized into two types: qualitative and quantitative. Primary data were collected using an evaluation checklist from the websites of the libraries in question. Secondary data were collected from the websites of the institution and the library being examined.

6. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Data analysis was conducted from November 20, 2024, to November 30, 2024. Qualitative and quantitative feedback were gathered in accordance with the evaluation checklists. Each time a cell (i.e., specific features in the checklists) was marked (with “√” for Yes and “×” for No), one point was allocated to each feature present in the library website under examination. The score assigned to a website represents the cumulative count of cells evaluated for that particular library webpage.

6.1. Qualitative Evaluation

There are 11 elements in the qualitative section of the checklist that are utilized to document information obtained from the main page of the institution library websites. One point was

awarded to an attribute of the institution library website when a specific item in the cell was highlighted with a check-mark symbol ("√").

The homepage of all institutions library websites examined includes the following information: genre, phone number, email, plugins, website language and content, browser, and version.

The Internet has facilitated institution library websites to host a variety of media, including text, images, audio, and video clips. This technology is employed on educational websites through an interactive video-conferencing laboratory to disseminate video lectures and conduct webinars or interviews with firms, thereby enhancing student placement opportunities.

Table 2: Descriptive Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Library name	×	√	√	×
2	Address	√	√	√	√
3	Genre (Type)	ac	edu	edu	edu
4	Fax No.	×	×	×	×
5	Phone No.	√	√	√	√
6	E-mail	√	√	√	√
7	Plugins required	√	√	√	√
8	language	English	English	English	English
9	Language of site content	English	English	English	English

10	Browser & Version	Chrome 6.0	Chrome 6.0	Chrome 6.0	Chrome 6.0
11	Others	×	×	×	×
	Total Score (Max. 11)	8(73%)	9(82%)	9(82%)	8(73%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Note:

1. BITSP=Birla Institute of Technology and Sciences, Pilani
2. MAHEM=Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka
3. OPJGU=OP Jindal Global University, Sonipat, Haryana
4. SNUGN=Shiv Nadar University, Greater Noida, NCR

Table 2 demonstrates that MAHEM and OPJGU library websites included all components except fax numbers and others, on the other hand BITSP and SNUGN included almost all components except for the library name, fax number and others. The language and content language of all library websites is uni-lingual (English).

MAHEM and OPJGU library websites achieved a good score of 09(82%), whereas BITSP and SNUGN got 08(73%) score in this category. The checklist for the Qualitative Analysis Section lacks numerical values. The final assessment of the library study webpages excluded these values.

6.2. Quantitative Evaluation

The quantitative section of the “checklist included 170 checkpoints designed on the pattern of Bharati & Madhusudhan to assess the library websites under investigation. The following checkpoints were included:

Multimedia features (18 questions), (ii) general features (16 questions), library service features (15 questions), and library resource features (28 questions). My Library features (13 questions), Web/Library 2.0 features (20 questions), currency, accuracy, and relevance features (10 questions), organization and structure features (15 questions), links and maintenance features (07 questions), user interface features (09 Questions), searching features (12 questions), and Informative Feedback and support features of study websites (07 questions) are intended to facilitate the collection of data.”

Quantitative responses were gathered from the websites using an evaluation checklist. One point was assigned to the corresponding feature of these library websites when a specific item in the cell was marked as ("√"). Twelve sections of the quantitative evaluation were analyzed, and each section was overseen by a rating.

6.2.1. Multimedia Features

Multimedia is “a critical component of any website and includes text, sound, video, animation, and/or images. Users are attracted to websites owing to their visual appeal, high-quality audio/video, and high-definition images. The aesthetics of a website are enhanced by high-quality multimedia features.” Table 3 illustrates the multimedia features, which encompass 18 items in a variety of features, including audio, video, animation/GIF, and graphic/icon/image features.

Table 3: Multimedia Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN

1	Audio contents	x	√	√	√
2	Textual description of external audio files	x	x	√	x
3	Audio icons clearly labelled	x	x	√	√
4	Files size of external audio files	x	x	x	x
5	Video contents	√	√	√	√
6	Video icons clearly labelled	√	x	√	√
7	Information about external video files	√	x	√	√
8	Files size of external video files	x	x	x	x
9	Animations/GIF feature available	√	x	x	√
10	Animations/GIF used to substrate websites	√	x	x	√
11	Animations/GIF files appropriate in the websites	√	x	x	√
12	Animations/GIF file enhance the websites	√	x	x	√
13	No disturbance of Animations/GIF files	√	x	x	√
14	Graphics/Image show the content	√	x	x	√
15	Graphics/Image suitable to information content	√	x	x	√
16	Icons/Image and other graphical representations are used constantly	√	x	x	√
17	Proper textual information for external images	x	x	x	x

18	Mentioned File size for external images	x	x	x	x
	Total Score (Max. 18)	11(61%)	2(11%)	6(33%)	13(72%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Table 3 indicates that among the multimedia options evaluated on the websites, SNUGN achieved the highest score of 13(72%), whereas MAHEM achieved the lowest score of mere 02(11%). However, this is not conclusive. The final score of the investigated websites is calculated by summing the scores from this table with those from other feature tables, specifically transferring the scores to the final score in Table 15.

6.2.2. General Features

“General information features help users to know the basic information about the library, including contact information, working hours, library rules, services, staff, mission statement and help features offered by the libraries.” (Madhusudhan and Ahmed, 2013).

Table 4: General Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Home	√	×	√	√
2	Mission	×	×	√	√
3	Staff Information	√	√	√	√
4	Opening Detail	√	√	√	√

5	Library rules and regulation	√	√	√	√
6	News and events	√	×	√	√
7	Contact Information	√	√	√	√
8	Frequently Ask Questions	√	×	√	√
9	Annual reports	×	×	√	√
10	Floor map/ site-map	×	×	√	√
11	Newsletter	×	×	√	√
12	Visitor number /Web counter	√	×	×	√
13	Library history	√	×	×	√
14	Library committee /Advisory committee	√	×	√	√
15	Photo/ Video gallery	√	×	√	√
16	Other information	√	×	√	√
	Total Score (Max. 16)	12(75%)	4(25%)	14(88%)	16(100%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Staff information, opening details of the library, library rules and regulations and contact numbers are critical components that offer insights into the personnel responsible for various functions within the library. These all information was present in all (100%) of the websites analyzed, as indicated in Table 4.

OPJGU and SNUGN library websites provided the next most common sections i.e. home and mission statement, as illustrated in Table 4.

SNUGN attained the highest score of 16(100%), whereas MAHEM obtained last place with a mere score of 04(25%), as illustrated in Table 4. Nonetheless, this is not a definitive conclusion. The final score of the analyzed websites is determined by aggregating the scores from this table with those from further feature tables, explicitly allocating the values to the final score in Table 15.

6.2.3. Library Services

This section discusses “the library services offered by the select institutions library websites to their patrons. Library services may encompass new arrivals, interlibrary loan (ILL), document delivery service (DDS), plagiarism detection tools, newspaper clippings, and librarian assistance, all of which are accessible through the library's website.” Table 5 compares the online library offerings of the four private Institutions of Eminence in India Library websites.

Table 5: Library Services Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	New arrival list	√	x	√	√
2	ILL/ DDS	√	x	√	√
3	Information literacy	√	√	√	√
4	Citation style tools	√	√	√	√

5	Online institutional tutorials	√	√	√	√
6	Information desk	√	√	√	√
7	Anti-Plagiarism Checking	√	√	√	√
8	Web Search tips	√	√	√	√
9	Newspaper clippings	x	x	x	x
10	Photo-copying service	x	√	√	√
11	Ask a librarian service via email	√	√	√	√
12	Ask a librarian service via call	√	√	√	√
13	Ask a librarian service via Instant Message (chat)	√	√	x	√
14	Ask a librarian service via online form	√	√	√	√
15	Other Services	√	√	√	√
	Total Score (Max. 15)	13(87%)	12(80%)	13(87%)	14(93%)

Note: (√) for Present and (x) for Absent

Table 5 illustrates the Information literacy, Citation style tools, Online institutional tutorials, Information desk, anti-plagiarism checking tools, Web Search tips, Ask a librarian service via email, call and online modes and other services are standard offerings on all the selected library websites. The SNUGN is providing all the services except News Clippings Service.

SNUGN offers 14 (93%) of the 15 library services, whereas MAHEM provides only 12(80%) of the same services on its website. MAHEM must enhance the functionality of its website.

6.2.4. Library Resources

This section presents “online library resources available on the websites of all selected institutions libraries.” Table 6 functions as a checklist of essential e-resources and the corresponding links to identify the library website housing them.

Table 6: Library Resources Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Links to electronic journals	√	√	√	√
2	Links to Bibliographic databases	√	√	√	√
3	Links to Subject guides	√	√	√	√
4	Web resource portal (English language)	√	√	√	√
5	Web resource portal (Hindi language)	x	x	x	x
6	Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC)	√	√	√	√
7	Links to Union Catalogue	√	√	√	√
8	Rare collections (special journal)	√	√	√	√
9	E-theses and E-dissertations	√	√	√	√
10	Links to Open Access (OA) Resources	√	√	√	√
11	Links to other reference sites	√	√	√	√
12	Links to electronic books	√	√	√	√

13	Links to Institutional Repository (IR)	√	√	√	√
14	Links to bound volumes	√	√	√	√
15	Links to search engines	√	√	√	√
16	Links for Digital library Consortia (e.g. INDEST AICTE/UGC Infonet Digital Library Consortia)	√	√	√	√
17	Other Library collections	√	√	√	√
18	Book Recommendation	×	√	√	√
19	Privacy policy	×	×	√	√
20	Links to Librarian's personal homepage	×	√	√	√
21	Webmaster address	×	√	×	×
22	Promotional materials for the library	√	√	√	√
23	Services for faculty member	√	√	√	√
24	Book reviews and other resources	√	√	√	√
25	Recruitment cells	√	√	√	√
26	Links to specific subject	√	√	√	√
27	Information for Disabled users	√	√	√	√
28	Remote Access Information	√	√	√	√
	Total Score (Max. 28)	23(82%)	26(93%)	26(93%)	26(93%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Table 6 delineates various common resources, including links to e-journals, bibliographic databases, Subject guides, Web resource portal (English language), OPAC, Union catalogs, Rare collections (special journal), E-theses and E-dissertations, open access (OA) resources, other reference sites, electronic books, institutional repositories (IR), bound volumes, search engines, digital library consortia, other library collections, Promotional materials for the library, Services for faculty member, Book reviews and other resources, Recruitment cells, Links to specific subject, Information for Disabled users and Remote Access Information, all of which are represented on all the selected library websites.

All the selected institutions got a good score of 26(93%) of the 28 library checkpoints except BITSP which includes only 23(82%) of the same resources on their website. BITSP must enhance the functionality of its website.

6.2.5. My Library

According to Liu (2008), “My Library Space is described as a comprehensive information environment tailored to the individual user, offering a combination of information technology tools. Furthermore, some library websites feature personalized spaces, often referred to as My Library, My Personal Library or My Search Space. These spaces aggregate various services into a single location, providing users access to their library accounts, course reserve materials, library alerts, databases, citation tools, and customized search preferences or results.”

My library is a unique feature of the selected library websites except MAHEM. Most of the library websites are having this fully user-oriented feature, which is presented in table 7.

Table 7: My Library features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	My library records	√	×	√	√
2	Links for Renew Books	√	×	√	√
3	Links for Reserve A Book	√	×	√	√
4	Latest information for users	√	√	√	√
5	The article of users Interest	√	×	√	√
6	Users books location	√	×	√	√
7	User preference books/journals	√	×	√	√
8	Detail information related to Library membership cards	×	×	×	×
9	Research guides and tools	√	×	√	√
10	Suggestion and recommendation for New E-Books/E-Journals and database	×	×	×	×
11	Visitors chart	×	×	×	×
12	Assistance in recovering full-text documents	√	×	√	√
13	List of Digital lecture	√	×	√	√
	Total Score (Max. 13)	10(77%)	1(8%)	10(77%)	10(77%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

“My Library record features are mainly created for the user only, with the help of membership ID and password, user want to see all the transaction record (like which book issues, which book

due and how much fine generated). Some features like; links for renew books, links for reserve a book, latest information for a user, and locate your book was in process. Some other features such as (user interest, user priority books, suggestions and recommendation for new e-books and assistance in recovering full-text documents) are provided by leaving the user's query through email. Visitors chart feature provide user list who visit in a library and digital reading list provide a facility of a searching lecture from the repository.” (Bharati ad Madhusudhan, 2019)

When it comes to offering these services on its library websites, BITSP, OPJGU and SNUGN scored 10(77%), whereas MAHEM scored only 01(08%). MAHEM library websites strongly need to enhance its presence in this category.

6.2.6. Web 2.0/ Library 2.0

“Web/Library 2.0 tools are most frequently used by the people. With this, the dissemination of information becomes easier for a great number of audiences” (Devi and Verma, 2017). Web2.0 tools covered blogs, RSS feeds, Wikipedia, social networking sites (SNS), Twitter, Facebook,LinkedIn, Google Plus, YouTube, and many others, as mentioned in Table 8.

Table 8: Web 2.0/Library 2.0 Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Blogs	x	x	x	√
2	RSS Feeds	x	x	√	x
3	Wikipedia	x	x	√	√

4	Social Networking Sites (SNS)	√	x	√	√
5	Google plus	x	x	√	x
6	Social Tagging and Bookmarking	x	x	x	x
7	File sharing	x	x	√	x
8	Video sharing	x	x	√	x
9	Calendaring	x	x	√	x
10	Image sharing	x	x	√	x
11	Library virtual tour	√	x	√	√
12	QR code for mobile phone	x	x	x	√
13	Folksonomies	x	x	x	x
14	Collaborative authoring	x	x	x	x
15	Weather detail	x	x	x	x
16	Podcasts	x	x	x	x
17	YouTube	x	x	√	√
18	Mobile Library icon	x	x	x	x
19	PlumX Metric	x	x	x	x
20	Instant Message	x	x	x	x
	Total Score (Max. 20)	2(10%)	0(00%)	10(50%)	6(30%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Table 8 demonstrates that most of selected library websites lacks Web 2.0 features, including Blogs, Really Simple Syndication (RSS) feeds, YouTube and Mobile Library icons.

OPJGU possesses highest score of 10(50%) features, whereas MAHEM received lowest score of 00(00%) features in offering such facilities on their library websites. All the library websites require significant enhancement in this category.

6.2.7. Currency, Accuracy, and Relevance

Website currency denotes the recency of the content or text present on the site. The website must be updated regularly to guarantee that appropriate individuals receive correct information in a timely manner. The date of the latest revision is a vital indicator of the material's currency and should be prominently displayed on every website's homepage and sub-pages.

“The copyright to electronic information is a complex area, and its general considerations are beyond the scope of this research. However, one consideration in terms of the evaluation is the availability of copyright information. Users may want to reuse textual or graphical materials such as publications or presentations. However, as a basic rule, any information published via the Internet will be covered by copyright, including images and web page text. It is, therefore, helpful if the authors or web admins provide a statement of the copyright owner of materials, details of how materials should be cited in a publication, or attributed to an author mentioning the institute official who should be contacted to obtain copyright permission where required. The copyright status and official name or logo of the IIM were found on all the study websites” (Madhusudhan, 2012).

“Accuracy generally refers to the correctness of the source of information. In many respects, the need to determine accuracy underpins the evaluation process. It is often why looking critically at any information and relevance is an important part of the evaluation process.” (Madhusudhan, 2012)

Table 9: Currency, Accuracy and Relevance Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	All links relevant to the web page	√	√	√	√
2	All links appropriate to the reference desk	√	×	√	√
3	Copyright mentions	×	×	×	×
4	Last updated information	×	×	×	×
5	Each page of the site include information about the date of the last update	×	×	×	×
6	Any indication of last updated/revised of the page	×	×	×	×
7	Any official logo of the organization present on the site	√	√	√	√
8	Official logo links to the home pages	√	√	√	√
9	No grammatical or spelling errors found in the website	√	√	√	√
10	links to other credible websites	√	√	√	√
	Total Score (Max. 10)	6(60%)	5(50%)	6(60%)	6(60%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Table 9 shows that all the selected library websites got 100% score in terms that all the links were relevant to the webpage, indication of official logo on their website, no grammatical/spelling mistakes present on their library websites as well as links to other credible websites.

Overall, BITSP, OPJGU and SNUGN contains 06(60%) features, whereas MAHEM contains 05(50%) features in providing such facilities on their library websites. The MAHEM needs to improve in this category as well.

6.2.8. Organization and Structure

A website's organization is crucial; "each page should be separate from the others, but there should be a good link between them so that visitors can easily go back to the one they were on before. Websites adhere to basic structural principles that reinforce a user's mental models of how information is organized and structured on the site." These principles guided the design process. According to Madhusudhan (2012), three main themes regarding web structures may be used to create dynamic and attractive websites.

Table 10: Organization and Structure Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Site accessible from different web browsers	√	√	√	√
2	Is the site having font size features?	×	×	×	×
3	Is the site having font colour features?	×	×	×	×
4	When the web page loads, all the graphics, images, and icons are present	√	√	√	√

5	Web Content arranged according to chronological, alphabetical, subject and numerical order	√	√	√	√
6	Organization of a resource is appropriate	√	√	√	√
7	A principle of arrangement obvious to the patron	√	√	√	√
8	Table of contents (TOC) or floor map or sitemap present on the site home page	√	√	√	√
9	Do not require proprietary software or password to access information	√	√	√	√
10	The actual coverage matches with the proposed mission	√	√	√	√
11	Areas and coverage are aligned with the needs of users	√	√	√	√
12	Is the subject matter coverage complete?	√	√	√	√
13	statement of the proposed audience is mentioned in the site	√	√	√	√
14	the terminology used is familiar to the proposed audience	√	√	√	√
15	visitor number/ lists/charts	×	×	×	√
	Total Score (Max. 15)	12(80%)	12(80%)	12(80%)	13(87%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Table 10 shows that all the selected library websites were acquired from various web browsers and found some common features such as loading graphics/image/icon/ file on home pages, an appropriate organization of a resource, the principle of arrangement obvious to the patron, and seeking information without any proprietary software or password.

Overall figures, SNUGN covers 13(87%) checkpoints, whereas all other websites covers only 12(80%) checkpoints. All library websites need to improve a lot in this category.

6.2.9. Links and Maintenance

The navigation system shows the user's current location, historical context, possible future paths, menu trees, arrows, and site maps. In addition to the page header and footer links, it contains the organization's name and logo details. Although it is a time-consuming task, the Webmaster or librarian must maintain the links (external and internal) because every navigation system provides a trail or clue that shows the client's true location on the webpage utilising any means.

Table 11: Links and Maintenance Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Describe the link in an appropriate way	√	×	√	√
2	Links clearly labelled	√	√	√	√
3	Link to move to the top of page	√	×	√	√
4	There any dead links/empty links	×	×	×	×
5	Reliability of internal links	√	√	√	√
6	Is the responsibility of site display given?	√	×	√	√
7	A library has feedback/comment facility available.	√	×	√	×
	Total Score (Max. 7)	6(86%)	2(29%)	6(86%)	5(71%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Table 11 shows that all the library websites have the same features as; links are clearly labelled and the reliability of internal link is also good. Overall, BITSP and OPJGU covered 06(86%) of the criteria, whereas MAHEM achieved the lowest score of 02(29%)I this category. MAHEM and SNUGN libraries need to add more facilities to upgrade their website.

6.2.10. User Interface

The User Interface/Support system comprises nine elements on our checklist. These points include a quick way to return to the homepage, an attractive design, a page that loads quickly, and so on. With this system, you will not have to worry about any annoying scrolling, blinking, blurring of text, annoying web ads, having to click more than three times to discover what you are looking for, a status message to let you know how the system is doing, and, if needed, online assistance and instructions.

“User interface is the area in which criteria for internet-based information sources differ most from other sources. A user interface is a system in which users interact with a machine. The user interface includes hardware (physical) and software (logical) components. User interfaces exist for various systems and provide a means of input (allowing the user to manipulate a system) and output (allowing the system to indicate the effects of the users’ manipulation.” (Madhusudhan and Ahmed, 2013).

Table 12: User Interface Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Navigation Aids are clearly labelled	√	√	√	√

2	Is a way of coming back to the home page for each page of the site	√	√	√	√
3	Any under construction page	×	√	√	√
4	Any types of information, for instance, text, symbols, graphics, image etc. clearly famed from each other features	√	√	√	√
5	Aesthetic presence is visually likable not messy or busy	√	√	√	√
6	Does it include links to the page title and a simple page identity	√	√	√	√
7	It is easy to use all the tasks provided by the system	√	√	√	√
8	It is easy to assess the use of websites to get the desired work	√	√	√	√
9	Web pages load faster	√	×	√	√
	Total Score (Max. 9)	8(89%)	8(89%)	9(100%)	9(100%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Table 12 indicates that all the navigational aids were clearly labelled. There is no under-construction page on any of the library website. The appearance of the webpage is clearly defined on all the library websites. Table 12 also indicates that aesthetic design and visual appeal with consistent page heading, ease of utilization of all functions provided by the system, and faster page loading were found in almost all library websites. The Overall figure, OPJGU and SNUGN covered 09(100%) of the checklists, on the other hand BITSP and MAHEM covered 08(89%) checklist in this category.

6.2.11. Searching Features

“Searching is the main goal of the users on the website is to find the information as quickly as possible” (Walia and Gupta, 2013).

Search functionality is a crucial aspect of websites, enabling users to find information by utilizing search operators, including Boolean operators, truncation, federated search, and keyword searching. This allows users to quickly obtain their desired results in seconds. Additionally, it offers the capability to modify the search query using the filter feature, which includes options such as organizing by subject, year, and publication.

This section provides information on several aspects of search functionality, including site search, search engine, keyword search, truncation search, Boolean search, federated search, modification of search results, history of search results, browser options, and search guidelines.

Table 13: Searching Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Search feature or search engine is available	√	x	√	√
2	Keyword / Title / Author search	√	x	√	√
3	Exact-match search	√	x	√	√
4	Federated Search	√	x	√	√
5	Truncation search	x	x	x	x
6	Boolean search	x	x	√	√
7	Adjacent search	x	x	x	x

8	Weighted Search	x	x	x	x
9	Many options to search on their home pages such as A-Z lists or general search	√	x	x	x
10	Display search result in an understandable format	√	x	√	√
11	A user can manipulate search results	√	x	√	√
12	Search guidelines clearly mention what to do	√	x	√	√
	Total Score (Max. 12)	8(67%)	0(00%)	8(67%)	8(67%)

Table 13 reveals that all the library websites, except MAHEM, offer essential search features, including keyword, title, and author searching; exact-match search; displaying search results in a clear format; and clearly stated search instructions. However, none of the websites utilize advanced search tools such as truncation, adjacent operators, or weighted searching.

Overall, the BITSP, OPJGU, and SNUGN library websites meet 8 out of 12 checkpoints (67%) in this category, whereas the MAHEM library website fulfills none of the checkpoints (0%). This highlights an urgent need for MAHEM to update and enhance its search features to improve its functionality and usability.

6.2.12. Informative Feedback and Support

Informative feedback and support features are the last criteria and include seven checkpoints, such as status related to messages and error information; the system allows the user to correct the error; help/feedback feature; how to use the help/feedback feature and exit; system instruction; and instructions clearly promote and indicate what to do, as highlighted in table 14.

Table 14: Informative Feedback and Support Features

S. No.	Particulars	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Status message present to indicate that the system is being or has been done	√	√	√	√
2	If errors occur when the system notifies the user	×	√	×	×
3	System allow the user to correct the errors	×	×	×	×
4	Support / Feedback feature is available	√	√	√	√
5	Explains the actions in relation to what the system is currently doing while using support/feedback features	√	√	√	√
6	Instructions clearly promote and indicate what to do	√	√	√	√
7	Instructions are completely worded on the site	√	√	√	√
	Total Score (Max. 7)	5(71%)	6(86%)	5(71%)	5(71%)

Note: (√) for Present and (×) for Absent

Table 14 shows that most of the library websites provide at-least five services out of seven in this checklist.

Overall figures, MAHEM received the highest score of 06(86%) in this particular checklist. Whereas, the BITSP, OPJGU and SNUGN received five points out of seven in this section. All studied libraries need to add a few other features to enhance their feedback feature.

7. Total Score and Rating Scale of the Study Websites

The total scores of the University websites under study are presented in Table 15, which is based on previous tables from table 03 to table 14.

Table 15: Total Score of the Websites

S.No.	Quantitative Evaluation Features	BITSP	MAHEM	OPJGU	SNUGN
1	Multimedia Features (18)	11	2	6	13
2	General Features (16)	12	4	14	16
3	Library Service Features (15)	13	12	13	14
4	Library Resource Features (28)	23	26	26	26
5	My Library Features (13)	10	1	10	10
6	Web/ Library 2.0 Features (20)	2	0	10	6
7	Currency, Accuracy and relevance Features (10)	6	5	6	6
8	Organisation and Structure Features (15)	12	12	12	13
9	Links and Maintenance Features (07)	6	2	6	5
10	User Interface Features (09)	8	8	9	9

11	Searching Features (12)	8	0	8	8
12	Informative Feedback and Support Features (07)	5	6	5	5
	Score Maximum (170)	116(68%)	78(46%)	125(74%)	131(77%)

A five-point rating scale was developed based on the total number of checkpoints achieved by the institutions' library websites out of 170 quantitative assessment points. The rating scale is defined as follows:

- (i) **137-170**: Excellent
- (ii) **103-136**: Above Average
- (iii) **69-102**: Average
- (iv) **35-68**: Below Average
- (v) **01-34**: Needs Improvement.

Table 15 shows that the library websites of BITSP, OPJGU, and SNUGN received overall scores of 116 (68%), 125 (74%), and 131 (77%), respectively. According to the ranking chart, these scores fall within the range of 103-136, classifying these websites as "Above Average." In contrast, the library website of MAHEM received a score of 78 (46%), placing it in the 69-102 range, which categorizes it as "Average."

While BITSP, OPJGU, and SNUGN library websites outperform MAHEM's website, this does not imply that they do not require improvement. All library websites should work toward enhancing their scores in various categories to achieve the "Excellent" rating.

8. Conclusion

The study assessed both the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of various aspects of library websites from private institutions of eminence. These aspects included multimedia features, general information features, library services features, library resources features, "My Library" features, Web 2.0/Library 2.0 features, as well as features related to currency, accuracy, relevance, organization, structure, links and maintenance, user interface, search capabilities, and informative feedback and support.

The qualitative findings indicate that most websites incorporate these features, effectively drawing patrons' attention to the information available on their platforms.

The quantitative findings reveal that the file sizes of audio and visual files are not displayed on any of the library websites studied. Additionally, web counter features were absent among the general features evaluated. Several key aspects of library services, such as dedicated services for faculty members, promotional materials for the library, and links to the librarian's homepage, were also found to be missing across all library websites.

The study highlights that most library websites need to incorporate more user-friendly Web 2.0 features, such as folksonomies, weather updates, podcasts, and PlumX metrics, to improve quality and bridge the gap between libraries and their patrons. It also revealed that content on these websites is not systematically organized in chronological, numerical, or alphabetical order. Additionally, essential search functionalities, such as weighted searches and adjacent operators, were found to be absent.

The study was limited to four private institutions recognized as institutions of eminence in India and relied on manual evaluation techniques for data collection. Based on the findings, it is

recommended that library websites adopt a user-centric approach to provide information with minimal effort, ensuring no time is wasted. Websites should become more interactive, efficient, and user-friendly by addressing the shortcomings identified in the study.

Furthermore, since libraries play a crucial role for users, librarians must consistently update their websites, eliminate broken links, and prioritize features such as visually appealing designs, seamless navigation, and efficient search capabilities.

Data Availability Statements

The data-sets generated during the current study are available on the official library websites of [BITS, Pilani, MAHEM, Manipal, OPJGU, Sonipat and SNUGN, NCR]. Respectively the links of the webpages are [www.bits-pilani.ac.in, www.manipal.edu, www.jgu.edu.in, www.snu.edu.in]

Disclosure Statement

The authors reported no potential competing interest.

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